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D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

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Abbreviations

ACA	Adaptive Conjoint Analysis
ACBC	Adaptive Choice-based-Conjoint
ATA	Actual Time of Arrival
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Customer
CBC	Choice-Based-Conjoint
CS	Case Study
CVA	Conjoint Value Analysis
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CS	Case study
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival.
GLOSA	Green Light Optimised Speed Advice
HB	Hierarchical Bayes
IIA	Independence from Irrelevant Alternatives
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
MLE	Maximum Likelihood Estimation

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POI	Point Of Interest
TLA	Traffic Light Assistance
TTG	Time to Green
UAB	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
WP	Work Package

Abstract

The knowledge of a product or service acceptability and their features users' preferences is a valuable tool for decision makers in order to customise new offerings and discover what does and what does not work when bringing it to market.

Conjoint analysis is a powerful market research method which allows learning how people make decisions and what they really value in products and services, presenting people with choices and then analysing what were the drivers for those choices. This is especially relevant in the ITS and (C-)ITS domains, where the deployment of innovations has been considered slow and fragmented.

In NEWBITS, a conjoint analysis has been performed over four different case studies carefully selected as representative of the landscape in Europe. The results extract the users' preferences in form of attributes importance and level utilities segmented according the characteristics of the case study and provide valuable information in the development of new business models in order to accelerate the (C-)ITS deployment.

Executive summary

This deliverable aims at providing useful information about the users' acceptability and preferences of the ITS innovations, performing a conjoint analysis over the NEWBITS case studies as representative of the ITS landscape in Europe.

Conjoint analysis is an advanced market research quantitative method used over the last decades in order to understand precisely how customers and markets value different elements of a service or product. It is an effective tool to inform strategic and tactical marketing decisions and can be used to estimate features interests or price sensitivity.

The analysis in the NEWBITS case studies has been designed and executed following the general methodology of the conjoint analysis and applying the most used method at the moment, the Choice-based-Conjoint analysis. Following this methodology, each case study has clearly defined its product/service, has identified its main attributes and levels and has performed a data gathering process via an online survey specially configured for their selected end-users, extracting their preferences in terms or attributes importance and levels utilities.

The results of the conjoint analysis complement the information extracted from the case studies market research analysis and compose a perfect basis for the development of new business models for ITS:

- Case study one, a carpooling service implemented in a specific area, shows that the promise of parking space, users' identification and communication tools for users are highly valued features.
- Case study two, a Traffic Light Assistance service, positions end-users as expecting "information directly usable" and depicts younger users of the service valuing more the technical features of the system (such as which devices provide the information and how).
- Case study three, a service providing tracking and optimising of freight container transport, shows the importance of offering a highly configurable service which can be adapted to the different needs coming from the position of the company within the logistic chain and the role of the end-user in the company. The tracking capabilities and the price of the service per container are the features affecting most the users' opinions.
- Case study four, a predictive maintenance service on rail transport is perceived as highly beneficial by the end-users because the overall safety increase and the financial improvement in terms of value for money and journey reliability.

1 Introduction

1.1 Description of T3.2 and key interrelations

T3.2 aims at extracting the main end-users preferences from the NEWBITS case studies through the implementation of a conjoint analysis. The main results of the conjoint analysis are the level of end-users' acceptability of the product/service defined by the case study and relevant information about their preferences which ultimately could serve for the customization of these products/services.

The relation of T3.2 with other project work packages can be seen in the following picture:

Figure 1 Diagram for key interrelations in NEWBITS

T3.2 is fed and supported by the results of previous task in the project, extracts useful information enriching the case studies details extracted in T2.3 and T3.1 and constitute a good basis and additional information in the development of new business models (T4.2) and the cost-benefit analysis (T5.1).

1.2 Objectives and structure of the document

T3.2 and this deliverable D3.3 main objective is to analyse services studied in the NEWBITS case studies (as representative of the ITS landscape) in terms of users' preferences, which characteristics are highly appreciated and which have a negative impact. This information is very valuable for decision makers in order to customise their products and/or services and avoid unnecessary costs.

The specific objectives for this deliverable, which are shared by all case studies, are:

- Target the right group of end-users in order to assure the appropriate data gathering process.

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- Define precisely the scope of the analysis, working with the case studies stakeholders on the definition of the product/service and the selection of the attributes and levels which will be used in the end-users survey and data analysis.
- Collect and analyse the data in order to elicit the users' preferences.

The deliverable is structured as follows:

Section 2 of this document presents the methodological approach, including an introduction about the conjoint analysis method and detailing the steps followed for the NEWBITS case studies.

Section 3 of this document presents the scope defined in each case study, presenting the attributes, levels and segmentation selected following the methodology detailed in the previous section.

Section 4 presents the results of the conjoint analysis providing information about the attributes' importance and the levels' utilities.

Section 5 extracts the conclusions of the overall process summarizing the work done and the main results.

The appendices of this document contain additional information such as survey samples from the NEWBITS case studies, the full results from the conjoint analysis and the characteristics of the conjoint tool used for the study.

2 Methodology

2.1 Conjoint analysis

Conjoint analysis [1] is one of the most widely-used quantitative methods in marketing research. It is used to measure preferences for product features, to learn how changes affect demand for products or services, and to forecast the likely acceptance of a product if brought to market [2].

Conjoint methods were based on work in the sixties by mathematical psychologists and statisticians Luce and Tukey (1964), and discrete choice methods came from econometrics, building upon the work of McFadden (1974), 2000 Nobel Prize winner in economics. The key characteristic of conjoint analysis is that respondents evaluate products or services profiles composed of multiple conjoined elements (attributes or features). Based on how respondents evaluate the combined elements (the product concepts), the preferences scores that they might have assigned to individual components of the product that would have resulted in those overall evaluations are deduced using statistical estimation techniques. The essence of the conjoint analysis is that it can be used in order to understand how buyers made complex purchase decisions, to estimate preferences and importance for product features and to predict buyer behaviour [3].

2.1.1 Brief history of conjoint analysis

Conjoint analysis has his earliest roots in psychology and the testing of theory that when people take decisions the result is the “sum” of all the bits of value for each part of that decision. It requires breaking a product down into its constituent parts building profiles from these parts, then gathering preference data and finally testing untried combinations to see if the customer preference was as expected [4].

The first tests were called full-profile designs (since the respondent saw profiles with one of each type of part) and were designed on cards using some form of ranking exercise. The major obstacle was in reducing the number of all possible profiles down to a manageable number, resulting in the use of “fractional factorial orthogonal design” to build the profiles to test (the same type of approach used in statistical process control and Taguchi methods [5] in operations management). The method of analysis initially was called ANOVA [6] or analysis of variance to produce a statistical model to predict the preference drivers. The result of the analysis was the calculation of “part-worths”, describing how much each variable contributes to the final model [4].

At the end of 1990s, the hybrid designs (so called because they do a combination of trade-off and non-trade-off elements) and the Adaptive Conjoint Analysis (ACA) were the most common form of conjoint analysis in use, although it tended to be disfavoured by academics because of the lack of a firm underlying theoretical model and the somewhat arbitrariness of the design. The demand for shorter (internet) surveys, the release of commercial software for discrete choice modelling and the arrival of techniques such as Hierarchical Bayes (HB), allowing choice-based data easier to analyse at a subgroup level, made choice-based conjoint (CBC) a much more common type of analysis. These developments came from the econometric world and in particular from researchers looking at “revealed preference” in behavioural economics, requiring a model describing how people make choices and a method for properly analysing the behaviours to be able to value the underlying preferences.

Describing the choice model in terms of a utility function [7] with appropriate error terms to account for unobserved factors was the first step. Developing a method of estimation (Maximum Likelihood Estimation – MLE) to enable factors to be estimated (and getting a set of solvable equations) was the second. In CBC, respondents indicate preferences not with an artificial ranking or rating, but choosing from a number of alternatives, a more realistic task. It also offers powerful benefits, such as including the ability to do a better job of modelling interactions (i.e. brand-specific demand curves), availability effects and cross-elasticities. In the other hand, as choosing provides less information than either ranking or rating, this was combined with an approach which aggregated analysis over the market as a whole, giving this particular form of conjoint a stronger theoretical background and since then, more studies have been choice-based than adaptive [3] [4].

2.1.2 Classification of conjoint analysis

The previous section presents an overview of the evolution over time of the different types of conjoint analysis, from the early rating-based systems (also known as Conjoint Value Analysis or CVA) to the first conjoint analysis software system (Adaptive Conjoint Analysis or ACA) to the modern Choice-based-Conjoint or CBC. This section aims at providing more details about the different types of conjoint analysis and offering some insight about the problems and advantages of each method.

The rating-based systems involve asking respondents to rate (or rank) series of concept cards. Another option is the best-worst conjoint where respondents are asked to indicate which option is the best and which option is the worst among three or more alternatives in each question. Since CVA uses to be full profile based (where all attributes are shown in every question), the big disadvantage is the limitation in the number of attributes (with more than six attributes overwhelming the respondents with too much information) [8] [9].

The ACA “adapts” to participants responses with varying sections of the interview that change based in the respondents’ previous answers. The main advantage of the ACA is the capacity to measure more attributes (a dozen or even two-dozen attributes) because the use of the partial profile approach but it is limited to be computer-based since the adaptation of the survey to respondents’ previous answers cannot be done in paper-based surveys. It also requires a long interview time because the large number of attributes [9].

CBC is the most common form of conjoint used at the moment. Usually it is based on the full profile approach, which sets a limitation in the amount of information a respondent can absorb at a time and limits the number of attributes to 5-7. In the other hand the set of possible profiles is spread across the sample, so typically each respondent sees 8-12 choice tasks [9][11]. There are several ways to analyse the choice results [9]:

- Aggregate choice analysis: this was the first method of analysis for CBC and it assumes respondent homogeneity (i.e. one utility vector for all respondents jointly), resulting in the assumption of the respondent utility equals the average utility, which is quite restrictive and does not allow for individual effects in the sample. This method also suffers from Independence from Irrelevant Alternatives (IIA), often referred as the Red Bus/Blue Bus problem.

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- Latent class analysis: this method detects homogeneous respondent segments and calculates segment-level-part-worths improving the predictability over aggregate choice models (i.e. individual respondent utility vectors composed of a combination of class vectors).
- Hierarchical Bayes Estimation [10]: this method “borrows” information from every respondent to improve the accuracy and stability of each individual’s part-worths (i.e. individual respondent utility vectors, assuming that each individual can only deviate so much from the aggregate utility vector). It reduces the IIA problem and improves the predictive validity of both individual-level models and market simulation share results.

The partial profile CBC allows increasing the number of attributes of the full profile CBC but since the data are spread quite thin, because each task has many attributes omissions, the response is still the less informative choice (a choice instead of a rating or ranking), requiring larger sample sizes to stabilise the results [9].

Last but not least, the Adaptive Choice-based-Conjoint (ACBC) combines aspects of the CBC and the ACA, asking respondents to identify initially the product closest to their ideal using a configurator (Build Your Own – BYO) question, building some product concepts similar to the BYO product, asking the respondents to consider them and finally taking the considered products forward to a choice tournament in order to identify the overall best concept. In this case, the sample size required is smaller than in CBC but the interviews take longer [9].

There are several factors to consider when selecting a conjoint method, such as:

- The number of attributes: if the study requires many attributes, ACA is preferred, meanwhile a small number of attributes (something between 3 and 7) favour CBC.
- Mode of interview: paper-based surveys can be implemented using CBC or CVA if the sample size is very small (less than 100 respondents).
- Interview time: CBC is a very good alternative for short interviews. With more than 8 attributes, ACBC is the best option.
- Pricing research: If price is one of the attributes, CBC and ACBC are the best options.
- The maturity level of the product or service. A less mature service will require more exploration of the attributes.

2.1.3 Conjoint analysis methodological approach

The following figure represents the methodological approach of a conjoint analysis and its different steps:

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Figure 2 Conjoint analysis methodological approach and main steps

The **problem definition** step consists in selecting the scope of the product or service, this is, selecting the exact way the product or service is going to be brought to the market and then break it down into the appropriate attributes (features) and levels (possible values for each attribute). A simple example can be seen in the following figure, showing a hypothetical smartphone product:

Figure 3 Example of conjoint attributes and levels [12]

It is very important to select both the attributes and levels carefully and following several rules such as not including too many attributes in order to not overwhelm respondents, use a clear language that customers understand, define the levels within each attribute as mutually exclusive, etc.

The **design of profiles** step is the first step conditioned by the different types of existing conjoint analysis. Basically, a profile is a representation of the product/service using a specific combination of levels per each attribute identified. In the example shown in the Figure 3, we can see there are 3 profiles (called “product concepts” in the figure) formed by different levels of the attributes defined for the smartphone product.

As it was explained in previous sections, there are different options to perform a conjoint analysis (CBC, ACA, CVA, ACBC, etc.) and the type of conjoint analysis selected impacts directly in the way to present options to customers or consumers (product profiles). Usually the decision is taken based on the number of attributes to be considered, the contact method and the time available for the survey.

Once this decision is taken, the data gathering process starts with the creation of the survey used to gather the customers’ responses, analysed in the next step in order to extract their preferences.

The **analysis of results** step is also affected by the type of conjoint analysis selected, which will be used to find out which product profiles are most preferred (e.g. choosing, ranking, rating). Usually customers segments are defined in order to serve as basis for differentiated marketing strategies.

This step also involves the decision of which statistical estimation approach will be used to conclude the utility value of each attribute and level (also known as part-worths). Some methods used in this step are linear regression [13] or Bayesian hierarchical.

The **simulation and optimisation** step is sometimes considered as an additional step for a conjoint analysis, being the result of the conjoint study the set of part-worths that quantify respondents’ preferences for each level of each attribute. The market simulator is usually considered an important tool resulting from a conjoint analysis project, used to convert raw conjoint data into something that a marketing analyst can use for what-if games in order to investigate new product designs, estimate demand curves and elasticities, define products for market segments and define pricing strategies [14].

Finally the **report** step consist basically in offering the results of the conjoint analysis, this is, showing a quantified picture of how customers make purchasing decisions. The results of the conjoint can help companies in determining what resources to use during the process of a new product development and reach a better marketing strategy.

2.2 NEWBITS case studies conjoint analysis methodology

For the NEWBITS case studies, the methodology followed mimics in most parts the steps of the conjoint analysis methodology depicted in the previous section.

Given the different nature of the NEWBITS case studies, (CS1 and CS2 being B2C oriented, CS3 and CS4 more B2B oriented and also the different end-users potentially targeted by each case study) an initial and preliminary phase was conducted where all CS leaders were instructed about the details of the conjoint analysis process and how to proceed during the initial steps, those requiring direct interaction with the CS stakeholders.

In this phase, detailed guidelines about the identification of attributes and levels, the selection of profiles and appropriate end-users were produced and several conference calls were carried out. The main purpose was to prepare the CS leaders for their meetings with stakeholders and how to orient them in the definition of their products/services and the rest of activities of the problem definition and design of profiles steps.

The **problem definition** step was performed by each CS leader meeting their main stakeholder(s) and started with the selection of end-users for the conjoint study. This selection of end-users has been supported by the WP6 NEWBITS Network and specifically from the identified key stakeholders in D6.1 Col configuration synthesis report. Afterwards, the definition of the CS product/service was shaped and the identification of the initial attributes and levels was performed along with the selection of the appropriate end-users' segmentation.

During this step a collective decision was taken, limiting the number of attributes to a manageable number (between 5 and 7) in order to not over-complicating the data gathering and analysis processes and avoiding the end-users exhaustion when filling the surveys. After refining the attributes and levels following the guidelines defined in the preliminary phase and obtaining the final ones, this step was concluded.

The details of this step can be found in **section 3**.

The **design of profiles** step was initiated with the selection of the conjoint analysis type to be used in the study. The method selected was CBC, as it was considered as the more adequate to be used in NEWBITS because of several reasons:

- It is the most common form of conjoint used at the moment.
- It is based in a full profile approach (a level from each attribute is shown in the product profile) but to alleviate the respondents' work, the set of possible profiles is spread across the sample (offering a reasonable amount of choice tasks to each respondent).
- It shows more than just two "products" at the same time, along with a "none-of-these" option which offers a more realistic choice decision to be evaluated.
- Fits well with the number of attributes selected for the NEWBITS case studies (5-7).
- The task of choosing a preferred concept is similar to what buyers actually do in the marketplace.
- Offers shorter questionnaires (10-20 mins) diminishing respondents' exhaustion.

The following point was the selection of profiles and the design of the end-users' survey. At this stage of the process, an alternative identified during previous steps was materialised. The foreseen total sample sizes (number of respondents from each case study), total number of profiles derived from the attributes selected and the potential difficulties (ensuing from these numbers) in the execution of the data analysis resulted in discarding semi-automatic methods (using, for example, mathematical methods for the selection of profiles, free online tools for the survey design and Excel files or other means for the data analysis) in favour of a commercial conjoint software.

After an exhaustive research of the several software tools available in the market, the final choice was the solution provided by Sawtooth Software¹, specifically one of the components designed to conduct CBC analysis and offering several facilities for the selection of profiles, the design of the survey and the analysis of the respondents' choices, covering the necessities of both this and the next step of the conjoint study. The full details about the main characteristics of the tool can be found in **Appendix 3** Sawtooth software discover component [15].

The details of this step can be found in **section 3**.

The **analysis of results** step was carried out after the data gathering process and was partially performed by the conjoint software. The main results of the software are the importance summary (value attached to each specific attribute for the end-users) and utilities summary (value attached to each of the levels of an attribute). The results coming from the software were prepared and categorised and can be found in **section 4**.

In NEWBITS, in order to enrich the raw conjoint results, a simple exercise of **simulation and optimisation** was performed, even when the products/services defined in all the case studies are not yet in the market. Three different service configurations were created to show the users' share of preferences: a basic service, an "intermediate" service including the most important levels (extracted from the conjoint results) and an "all-in" service. A "none" option was also included in order to illustrate the share of users no interested in the service. In addition, the full raw results of the conjoint analysis will be available for the NEWBITS case studies stakeholders in case they decide to use them when bringing their products/services to the market.

The **report** step consists in both the full results of the conjoint analysis (which could be used by the NEWBITS case studies stakeholders in their future marketing strategies) and this document, which presents the main results obtained from the analysis.

¹ Sawtooth Software <http://www.sawtoothsoftware.com/>

3 Case studies scope

The definition of the case studies scope, based in the **problem definition** and the **design of profiles** steps of the conjoint methodology consisted in defining the following points:

- The definition of the product/service.
- The selection of the attributes and levels.
- The end-users segmentation.
- The creation of the end-users survey.

This section presents the different results, coming from these conjoint steps for all the NEWBITS case studies.

3.1 Case Study 1

3.1.1 Definition of the product/service

Case study 1 defined a carpooling system supported by an App, focused on a specific territory, in this case, on the Bellaterra campus of the UAB, making possible to travel to and from Bellaterra in a more efficient way. This includes, among other aspects, reducing time, saving costs, adapting infrastructures, reducing environmental impact and, ultimately, improving the mobility experience of users.

3.1.2 Attributes and levels

The attributes and levels defined for the CS1:

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Parking access	No	Not in rush hours	Always
Messaging	No	Only incidents	Chat
Users' rating	No	Yes	
Users' identification	No	Access only with NIU UAB	
Travellers matching	No	Yes, according to preferences and likings	
Information on environmental savings	None	Simple	Complete

Table 1 CS1 attributes and levels

As can be seen in the table, CS1 was broken down in 6 attributes:

- **Parking access:** the service allows access to a dedicated parking space for the carpooling service users.
 - Always.
 - Not in rush hours: the parking space will still be dedicated to the service users all time except during rush hours (during these periods the parking space will be shared with everyone).
 - No: there is not dedicated parking space for the service users.
- **Messaging:** a communication functionality allowing users of the service receiving notifications of the trip or a chat for users.
 - Chat: a chat for the users so they can communicate with one another.
 - Only incidents: the service only sends incidents information (such as delays or cancelations).
 - No: the service does not include any communication function for the end-users.
- **Users' rating:** the service allows providing feedback based in the users experience (assigning a good or bad rating to the driver and passengers).
 - Yes.
 - No.
- **Users' identification:** the service provides identification functionality so only identified users can use the service.
 - Access only with NIU UAB: only users with the University unique identification can access the service.
 - No: everyone can access the service.
- **Travellers matching:** the service takes into consideration the trip preferences from the users when creating the group for the trip.
 - Yes.
 - No.
- **Information on environmental savings:** the service provides information about the reduction of CO2, time, petrol, etc.
 - Complete.
 - Simple.
 - None.

3.1.3 Segmentation

In CS1, the end-users were segmented by their age, their gender, their relationship with the UAB, the frequency of their access to the campus and the distance from the origin to the UAB. The following table shows the different identified segments:

Age	18-25	26-35	36-55	56-65	More than 66
Gender	Male	Female	Other		
Relation with the UAB	Student	Teaching staff or Researcher	Administration and Services Staff	Provider, service provider or similar	Others
Access	4 days per	Between 1	Sometimes	Occasionally	

frequency	week more	or	and 3 days per week	per month		
Distance from the origin to the UAB	Less than 20 km		Between 21 and 50 km	More than 50 km		

Table 2 CS1 segmentation

3.1.4 CBC Survey

CS1 survey was conducted in Spanish and was composed by an introduction including a short explanation about the system, 5 segmentation questions and 12 choice tasks where the attributes and levels were presented to the respondents so they could select their preferred option. In this case and since the end-users were familiar with the characteristics of the system from recent pilots in the campus, a light explanation was considered enough for them in order to proceed with the survey.

A survey sample can be found in **Appendix 1** Case studies CBC surveys samples.

3.2 Case Study 2

3.2.1 Definition of the product/service

Case study 2 defined a Traffic Light Assistance (TLA) service, aiming at providing road drivers with the information to take the required driving actions when approaching traffic lights in urban areas and ultimately allowing them to avoid unnecessary stops and waiting times at urban intersections. This results in concrete traffic congestions improvements in urban areas as well as environmental and health-related benefits.

3.2.2 Attributes and levels

The attributes and levels defined for the CS2:

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Information type	GLOSA	TTG	GLOSA and TTG
Device	Smartphone	Car dashboard	Smartphone and car dashboard
Operating system	iOS	Android	iOS and Android
Notification type	Visual	Voice	Visual and voice
Information level	Information provided by the TLA service	Information provided by the TLA service and traffic events	Information provided by the TLA service, traffic events and

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
			POI

Table 3 CS2 attributes and levels

As can be seen in the table, CS2 service was broken down in 5 attributes:

- **Information type:**
 - GLOSA (Green Light Optimised Speed Advice): providing users with the information about the speed drivers must take in order to reach the next traffic light during the green period.
 - TTG (Time to Green): providing users with the information about the time to be waited until the traffic light switches back to green.
 - GLOSA and TTG: the service offers both types of information.
- **Device:** The information will be displayed in a smartphone or directly in the car dashboard.
 - Smartphone.
 - Car dashboard.
 - Smartphone and car dashboard.
- **Operating system:** the service will be available for the main operating systems.
 - iOS.
 - Android.
 - iOS and Android.
- **Notification type:** the service information is delivered in a visual way or through voice notifications.
 - Visual.
 - Voice.
 - Visual and voice.
- **Information level:** the service provides TLA information, traffic events information and information about Points of Interest (such as hotels, campsites or fuel stations).
 - Information provided by the TLA service: GLOSA and/or TTG only.
 - Information provided by the TLA service and traffic events.
 - Information provided by the TLA service, traffic events and POI.

3.2.3 Segmentation

In CS2, the end-users were segmented by their age, their gender, their income level, the purpose of the trip and the average distance for their most frequent trips. The following table shows the different identified segments:

Age	18-24	25-34	35-44	45-54	55-64	More than 64	
Gender	Male	Female	Other				
Income level	Below 5.000€	Between 5.000€ and 10.000€	Between 10.000€ and 20.000€	Between 20.000€ and 30.000€	Between 30.000€ and 50.000€	Between 50.000€ and 80.000€	Over 80.000€

Trip purpose	Home-based work trips	Home-based education trips	Non home-based trips travelling for business or education	Home-based other trips (leisure)	Non home-based other trips		
Trip distance	Between 0 and 5 km	Between 5 and 10 km	Between 10 and 15 km	Between 15 and 20 km	Between 20 and 30 km	Over 30 km	

Table 4 CS2 segmentation

3.2.4 CBC Survey

CS2 survey was conducted in Italian and was composed by an introduction including an explanation about the system along with a detailed explanation of some concepts (such as TLA, GLOSA, TTG or POI), 5 segmentation questions and 12 choice tasks where the attributes and levels were presented to the respondents so they could select their preferred option.

A survey sample can be found in **Appendix 1** Case studies CBC surveys samples.

3.3 Case Study 3

3.3.1 Definition of the product/service

Case study 3 defined a track-and-trace service for container transport from the sea port to the hinterlands by inland waterway and truck (for the last mile of the container to the warehouse). The service visualises in a dashboard the real-time status, location and Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) of containers from the moment the sea port is approached up to the moment at which the container reaches the warehouse where the container is unpacked, providing the following information:

- A centralised overview of the container planning.
- Continuously updated ETA.
- Actual Time of Arrival (ATA).
- Container status (e.g. customs information, commercial release).

This information stems from several sources, such as the individual participants' planning and monitoring systems as well as public sources for ship positioning and proprietary ETA predicting engines. The information is aggregated to complete an end-to-end view of the container, following an open standard for trip specification.

3.3.2 Attributes and levels

The attributes and levels defined for the CS3:

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Coverage of shipments	70% of shipments	85% of shipments	95% of shipments
Communication via service dashboard	Not via service	Chat function	Chat function and documents
Notification of deviations	No active messaging	Daily overview of deviations	Push message about deviations
Container condition	No info	Manual registrations	Manual and sensor information
Container selection	Not possible	Possible	
Tracking truck transport	Excluding truck transport	Including truck transport	
Price	30€ / container	20€ / container	10€ / container

Table 5 CS3 attributes and levels

CS3 was broken down in 7 attributes:

- **Coverage of shipments:** The share of shipments in planning that can be tracked can vary, depending on the amount of logistic partners needing to be connected
 - 70% of the shipments can be covered by the service.
 - 85% of the shipments can be covered by the service.
 - 95% of the shipments can be covered by the service
- **Communication via service dashboard**
 - Not via service: there isn't any communication option provided by the service.
 - Chat function: the service can simplify communications among the logistic chain parties by means of a chat function integrated in the dashboard.
 - Chat function and documents: the service includes the chat option and grant access to relevant transport documents.
- **Notification of deviations:**
 - No active messaging: the service does not send any message when a deviation occurs.
 - Daily overview of deviations: a daily summary of deviations between the scheduled time and the ETA.
 - Push message about deviations: a real-time messaging for a deviation between the scheduled time and the ETA.
- **Container condition:**
 - No info: the service does not provide any information about the container.
 - Manual registrations: the service includes additional information such as manual entries being registered within the logistic chain (e.g. damage detected, inspections, etc.).

- Manual and sensor information: the service includes manual information along with specific sensors able to continuously register the sealing or inner climate of the container.
- **Container selection:** the service allows the selection of containers from the planning the user want to see the track-and-trace applied to.
 - Not possible: all containers from the user schedule are monitored.
 - Possible: the user can purchase the service for containers from a specific customer or via a specific terminal.
- **Tracking truck transport:** the service can include last-mile truck transport (and truck transport as a last minute alternative for inland shipping).
 - Excluding truck transport: tracking from seaport to inland terminal but no last-mile truck transport.
 - Including truck transport: containers are followed throughout the entire route
- **Price:** the service price per track-and-traced container.
 - 30€ per container.
 - 20€ per container.
 - 10€ per container.

3.3.3 Segmentation

In CS3, the end-users were segmented by their company position in the logistic chain, their job within the company, the amount of containers transported and the share of containers transported per year from seaport. The following table shows the different identified segments:

Company position	Shipper	Freight forwarder	Carrier truck	Inland shipping	Inland terminal operator	Sea terminal operator	Warehousing	
Function within the company	Logistic employee	Logistic manager	Customer service	General manager	Chain employee / dispatcher	IT Manager	Other	
Number of container	<50 TEU per year	50-100 TEU per year	100-500 TEU per year	500-1.000 TEU per year	1.000 - 5.000 TEU per year	5.000-10.000 TEU per year	10.000 - 50.000 TEU per year	>50.000 TEU per year
Share of container via inland terminal	<50%	>50%	None					

Table 6 CS3 segmentation

3.3.4 CBC Survey

CS3 survey was conducted in Dutch and was composed by an introduction including an explanation about the system along with an detailed explanation of the attributes and levels, 15 choice tasks where the attributes and levels where presented to the respondents and finally 4 questions about segmentation (in this case, the segmentation questions were placed at the end of the survey in order for respondents to not be affected in their responses by the size of their companies or the number of containers transported by them).

A survey sample can be found in **Appendix 1** Case studies CBC surveys samples.

3.4 Case Study 4

3.4.1 Definition of the product/service

Case study 4 is a predictive maintenance solution utilising leading edge developments in computational intelligence to analyse railway data for the purpose of forecasting malfunctions of different components of the railway infrastructure. The solution uses and exploits Big Data to inform decision making in key areas such as cost reduction and efficiency of the rail industry, which affects all stakeholders and rail customers in particular. The system provides informed recommendations for the optimisation of the allocation of human resources and the timely repair/replacement of equipment, enabling Network Rail (owner of the infrastructure in UK), train operators companies, rolling-stock operators and stakeholders to reduce maintenance costs, increase network availability and improve maintenance efficiency.

3.4.2 Attributes and levels

The attributes and levels defined for the CS4:

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Value for money	3% increase in revenue	2% increase of revenue	1% increase in revenue
Journey reliability	5% less delays in services	3% less delays in services	1% less delay in services
Safety	Reduction of accidents with identification of the causes	Reduction of accidents but with no identification of the causes	No overall reduction of accidents
Lower cost/price in fee for the infrastructure	Cost reduction by 7%	Cost reduction by 5%	Cost reduction by 2%
Reputation	5% increase in travellers/freight	3% increase in travellers/freight	No increase

Table 7 CS4 attributes and levels

CS4 was broken down in 5 attributes:

- **Value for money:** Due to better maintenance efficiency, the train operators companies would obtain a better infrastructure for the price they are paying to the infrastructure owner, resulting in an overall increase in revenues in their daily operations.
 - 1% increase in revenue.
 - 2% increase in revenue.
 - 3% increase in revenue.
- **Journey reliability:** the predictive maintenance system allows the reduction in service delays.
 - 1% less delays in services.
 - 3% less delays in services.
 - 5% less delays in services.
- **Safety:** the predictive maintenance system results in a reduction of accidents and the identification of the causes.
 - No overall reduction of accidents.
 - Reduction of accidents but no identification of the causes.
 - Reduction of accidents with identification of the causes.
- **Lower cost/price in fee for infrastructure:** an overall better optimised infrastructure could allow a reduction of the fee paid by the train operators companies to the infrastructure owner.
 - Cost reduction by 2%.
 - Cost reduction by 5%.
 - Cost reduction by 7%
- **Reputation:** an overall better service results in an increase number of travellers and freight for the train operator companies.
 - No increase in travellers/freight.
 - 3% increase in travellers/freight.
 - 5% increase in travellers/freight.

3.4.3 Segmentation

In CS4, the end-users were segmented by their region of main business, the mode of train transport provided and the distances covered. The following table shows the different identified segments:

Region of main business	London	West Midlands	East Midlands	South West	North East	Other
Type of train transport	Passenger	Freight	Both			
Distances covered	Long distance	Short distance	Both			

Table 8 CS4 segmentation

3.4.4 CBC Survey

CS4 survey was conducted in English and was composed by an introduction including an explanation about the system, 3 segmentation questions and 10 choice tasks where the attributes and levels were presented to the respondents so they could select their preferred option. In this case the number of choice task was reduced (from 12 to 10) in order to avoid respondents' exhaustion.

A survey sample can be found in **Appendix 1** Case studies CBC surveys samples.

4 Case studies conjoint results

This section presents the main results of the conjoint analysis for the NEWBITS case studies. Per each case study, the number of respondents per segmentation is presented along with the attributes importance and the utility summary. In the case of the utility summary only relevant values are included (since dual values benefit-not benefit are always expressed in the same number value, with a positive rating for the beneficial level and an equal negative rating for the non-beneficial level).

The full conjoint results can be found in **Appendix 2** full conjoint results.

4.1 Interpreting the results

When interpreting the results of the attributes importance and levels utilities, it is important to describe the measures and how to read quantitative data.

- Attribute importance is expressed as a percentage of how much difference each attribute could make in the total utility of a product. Importance measures are ratio-scaled but also relative, study-specific measures. Percentages from relative ranges result in set of importance values that add to 100 percent, as in the following example:

Attribute 1 importance = 35%

Attribute 2 importance = 20%

Attribute 3 importance = 45%

Total importance = 100%

- Level utilities or part-worths are scaled to an arbitrary additive constant within each attribute and are interval data (Celsius scale is an example of interval scale, it takes the same amount of heat to raise the temperature of a cup of water from 10 to 20 degrees as from 20 to 30 degrees. The zero point is arbitrarily tied to the freezing point of distilled water). The arbitrary origin of the scaling within each attribute results from dummy coding in the design matrix and the utilities are scaled to sum zero within each attribute, as in the following example:

<i>Attribute 1</i>	<i>Utility</i>
Level 1	-1.0
Level 2	0.0
Level 3	1.0

4.2 Case Study 1

4.2.1 Number of respondents

Case study 1 had a total of 1,128 respondents. The respondents are segmented as follows:

Figure 4 CS1 age segmentation

Age	Respondents	%
18-25	696	62%
26-35	134	12%
36-55	231	20%
56-65	58	5%
More than 65	9	1%

Table 9 CS1 age segmentation

Figure 5 CS1 gender segmentation

Gender	Respondents	%
Male	392	35%

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Female	729	65%
Other	7	1%

Table 10 CS1 gender segmentation

Figure 6 CS1 relation with UAB segmentation

Relation UAB	Respondents	%
Student	761	67%
Teaching staff or researcher	172	15%
Administration and services staff	188	17%
Provider, service provider or similar	1	0%
Other	6	1%

Table 11 CS1 relation with UAB segmentation

Figure 7 CS1 trip frequency segmentation

Trip frequency	Respondents	%
4 days per week or more	939	83%
Between 1 and 3 days per week	146	13%
Sometimes per month	22	2%
Occasionally	21	2%

Table 12 CS1 trip frequency segmentation

Figure 8 CS1 trip distance segmentation

Trip distance	Respondents	%
Less than 20 km	573	51%
Between 21 and 50 km	444	39%

More than 50 km	111	10%
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Table 13 CS1 trip distance segmentation

4.2.2 Attributes importance

The general attributes importance can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 9 CS1 general attributes importance

The general results show that the promise of a dedicated parking space for the users of the carpooling service is the most important attribute (valued almost twice important than the second and third attributes). The rest of attributes are valued more or less equally with a slight preference for the messaging attribute and the users' identification.

The segmented results:

Figure 10 CS1 attributes importance by age

The different age segments still value the parking access as the most desirable attribute but in this case it is important to notice that users' identification attribute is also very important for the end-users, especially for the older segment with an importance value of 27% being very

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close to the main attribute (parking access) values which range between 27.3% and 34%. The graph shows that the youngest segment give more importance to the messaging functionality meanwhile this importance about the communication is diluted in favour of the feeling of security (users' identification) for older segments.

Figure 11 CS1 attributes importance by gender

In this case we can see there is not much variation depending on the gender, the total numbers are very close to the general values.

Figure 12 CS1 attributes importance by relation with the UAB

Interestingly (although we should consider the sample size N=1 for the representativeness of the values), the segment composed by “providers, service providers and similar” value the most the users' identification functionality (40%). The messaging functionality (28.2%) is valued very close to the parking access (29.9%), meanwhile other attributes are pretty much not valued at all (less than 0.9%). Other segments such as students, teachers and administrative staff are closer to the general attribute numbers.

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Figure 13 CS1 attributes importance by trip frequency

In this case the different segments are similar to the general values with end-users traveling “sometimes per month” valuing more the users’ identification (24.3%) and the messaging functionality (19.7%) being very close to the parking access (20.9%).

Figure 14 CS1 attributes importance by trip distance

Finally, the end-users show no special preference distinct than the general values depending on their trip distance. Parking access is still the most desirable attribute (from 28.2% to 29.2%) and messaging and users’ identification functionalities are also very attractive attributes.

4.2.3 Utility summary

Figure 15 CS1 parking access levels utility

We can observe that the perceived value of the dedicated parking access is higher moving from partial access (not in rush hours) to a total access than from no dedicated parking to a partial parking access. It reinforces the importance of the attribute and also indicates that a service providing and exclusive parking total access is going to have very high acceptance.

Figure 16 CS1 messaging levels utility

For the messaging levels' values we can see that the chat is the most preferred functionality although going from a lack of communication to the notification of incidents is a more important step than providing the chat option.

Figure 17 CS1 information on environmental savings levels utility

Similarly, in case of the information of environmental savings, going from no information to simple information is more important than delivering complete information versus the simple information option.

4.2.4 CS1 market simulation and conclusions

In order to provide additional details to the raw conjoint results, a market simulation is presented using 3 different service configurations, basic, intermediate (including the preferred levels of the most important attributes) and all-in. A “none” option has been included in order to show the market share of users not interested in the service:

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Parking access	No	Always	Always
Messaging	Only incidents	Only incidents	Chat
Users' rating	No	No	Yes
Users' identification	No	Access only with NIU UAB	Access only with NIU UAB
Travellers matching	No	No	Yes, according to preferences and likings
Information on environmental savings	None	Simple	Complete

Table 14 CS1 market simulation first service configurations

The resulting share of preference using these configurations:

Figure 18 CS1 initial market simulation

As we can see, the all-in service is getting a much higher preference over the other 2 products. After running some more simulations, we found out that in order to reduce this gap is necessary to raise most of the attributes levels to be similar to the all-in service:

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Parking access	No	Always	Always
Messaging	Only incidents	Chat	Chat
Users' rating	No	Yes	Yes
Users' identification	No	Access only with NIU UAB	Access only with NIU UAB
Travellers matching	No	Yes, according preferences and likings	Yes, according preferences and likings
Information on environmental savings	None	Simple	Complete

Table 15 CS1 market simulation second service configurations

The resulting graph from these configurations:

Figure 19 CS1 second market simulation

We can observe that very similar services (only varying the information on environmental savings from “simple” to “complete”) still cause an important variation in users’ preferences.

Finally, in order to illustrate the importance of the parking access attribute, a third configuration was created equalling the intermediate configuration to the all-in configuration in all levels except the parking access:

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Parking access	No	Not in rush hours	Always
Messaging	Only incidents	Chat	Chat

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Users' rating	No	Yes	Yes
Users' identification	No	Access only with NIU UAB	Access only with NIU UAB
Travellers matching	No	Yes, according preferences and likings	Yes, according preferences and likings
Information on environmental savings	None	Complete	Complete

Table 16 CS1 market simulation third service configurations

The resulting graph from these configurations:

Figure 20 CS1 third market simulation

As we can see the product 2, counting with the rest of advantages as the product 3 except the total and dedicated access to the parking space, is much less preferred, illustrating the importance of the parking space attribute and how this affects the service acceptability.

The results extracted from case study one show the following conclusions:

- Users have high resistance to share a vehicle. In order to break that resistance, a carpooling service must be perceived as very advantageous offering as many distinct benefits as possible, such as parking space, communication functionalities, security and additional information (users, environmental).
- The promise of a dedicated parking space access is the most valued feature highly increasing the service acceptability.
- The messaging functionality is valued by younger segments while this importance moves towards the users' identification on older segments. It is important to configure the service according these values and depending on the demand segmentation.

- Regarding the messaging functionality, the service providing at least notification of the incidents is going to increase the users' acceptance, with the chat option perceived "as a bonus" but still impacting importantly in the service acceptability.
- The information on environmental savings is perceived as a secondary feature.

4.3 Case Study 2

4.3.1 Number of respondents

Case study 2 had a total of 116 respondents. The respondents are segmented as follows:

Figure 21 CS2 gender segmentation

Gender	Respondents	%
Male	58	50%
Female	58	50%
More than 65	0	0%

Table 17 CS2 gender segmentation

Figure 22 CS2 age segmentation

Age	Respondents	%
18-24	24	21%
25-34	22	19%
34-44	29	25%
45-54	24	21%
55-64	17	15%
More than 64	0	0%

Table 18 CS2 age segmentation

Figure 23 CS2 income segmentation

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Income	Respondents	%
Less than 5,000€	12	10%
5.000€-10.000€	7	6%
10.000€-20.000€	12	10%
20.000€-30.000€	32	28%
30.000€-50.000€	34	29%
50.000€-80.000€	14	12%
More than 80.000€	5	4%

Table 19 CS2 income segmentation

Figure 24 CS2 trip purpose segmentation

Trip purpose	Respondents	%
Home-based work trips	44	38%
Home-based education trips	37	32%
Non home-based trips travelling for business or education	17	15%
Home-based other trips (either for shopping and leisure purposes)	14	12%
Non home-based other trips	4	3%

Table 20 CS2 trip purpose segmentation

Figure 25 CS2 trip distance segmentation

Trip distance	Respondents	%
Between 0 and 5 km	8	7%
Between 5 and 10 km	26	22%
Between 10 and 15 km	22	19%
Between 15 and 20 km	25	22%
Between 20 and 30 km	18	16%
More than 30 km	17	15%

Table 21 CS2 trip distance segmentation

4.3.2 Importance

The general attributes importance can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 26 CS2 general attributes importance

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

The results show that the end-users give the most importance to the information type which is the core functionality of the service. The rest of attributes are valued more or less equally with a slight preference for the operating system and the notification type.

The segmented results:

Figure 27 CS2 attributes importance by gender

The different gender segments are very close to the general results with males valuing slightly more the information type and females, even valuing the information type as most important, giving a bit more value than males to the operating system.

Figure 28 CS2 attributes importance by age

In the case of the segmentation by age, the clear differentiator is young people, probably more in contact with technology, giving more importance to the operating system (30.5%). The notification type (20.3%) is very close to the information provided by the service (22.3%). The rest of segments are very close to the general attribute values although we can still see a clear balance of importance in young people for the rest of attributes in comparison with the predominant general value for the information type attribute.

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Figure 29 CS2 attributes importance by income

The level of income segmentation shows similar results to the age segmentations, mainly in the lowest levels (which probably are again corresponding with younger people). In this case, the operating system is the predominant attribute (33%) meanwhile the rest of attributes are quite balanced with the notification type (23.9%). The rest of segments are very similar to the general attributes values.

Figure 30 CS2 attributes importance by trip purpose

Observing the trip purpose segmentation, there are almost no differences with the general attributes values, if any, the segment traveling for home-based education trips (which is again probably influenced by young people still in their educational phase and with low levels of income) show a light deviation for the operating system attribute (23.4%) which in this case is not so noticeable against the information type attribute (39.7%).

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Figure 31 CS2 attributes importance by trip distance

Last but not least, it seems that medium distance travellers value more the type of information provided by the service rather than the operating system meanwhile short and longer trips give higher importance to the operating system even when they still value more the information type attribute.

4.3.3 Utility summary

Figure 32 CS2 information type levels utility

In this case the level utilities show a clear preference for the TTG functionality against the GLOSA functionality. A potential cause for this could be the drivers' feeling of control over their reactions counting with the TTG information in opposition to the biased control coming from the GLOSA information (affected by other drivers for example).

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Figure 33 CS2 device levels utility

The end-users clearly prefer the information available both in their smartphones and the car dashboard but the results show that if they need to select only one of them, they prefer their smartphones over the car dashboard (in opposition to what was stated initially during the pilot phase of the service within the Compass4D project). In any case, the ability of delivering the information to both devices is perceived as more important than making it available in the smartphone versus only having it on the car dashboard.

Figure 34 CS2 operating system levels utility

End-users prefer the service available on Android rather than in iOS (corresponding with the mobile operating system market share in Europe [16]) but making the service available in both OS is more important than moving from iOS-only to Android-only.

Figure 35 CS2 notification type levels utility

The results show end-users prefer voice notifications rather than visual-only information but making the service deliver both types of information is preferred versus the information coming through voice instead of a visual display.

Figure 36 CS2 information level levels utility

The results show that end-users prefer all levels of information (TLA, traffic events and POI) provided by the service and this preference grows equally with each level of information, this is, the addition of traffic events to the TLA is perceived equally as good as the addition of the POI to the TLA and traffic events information.

4.3.4 CS2 market simulation and conclusions

The market simulation in this case study also used 3 different service configurations, basic, intermediate (including the preferred levels of the most important attributes) and all-in. A “none” option has been included in order to show the market share of users not interested in the service:

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Information type	TTG	GLOSA and TTG	GLOSA and TTG
Device	Smartphone	Smartphone	Smartphone and car dashboard
Operating system	Android	iOS and Android	iOS and Android
Notification type	Visual	Visual and voice	Visual and voice
Information level	Information provided by the TLA service	Information provided by the TLA service and traffic events	Information provided by the TLA service, traffic events and POI

Table 22 CS2 market simulation first service configurations

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

The resulting share of preference using these configurations:

Figure 37 CS2 initial market simulation

Interestingly, the intermediate product is slightly less preferred than the basic product. After running some more simulations, we found out that “upgrading” the intermediate service to be delivered in the smartphone and the car dashboard only made the preference for the product 1 and 2 equal and “upgrading” the notification type to visual and voice placed again the product 2 in third position. Swapping the notification type to only “voice” and upgrading the information type to include TLA, traffic events and POI revealed a true “intermediate” product:

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Information type	TTG	GLOSA and TTG	GLOSA and TTG
Device	Smartphone	Smartphone and car dashboard	Smartphone and car dashboard
Operating system	Android	iOS and Android	iOS and Android
Notification type	Visual	Voice	Visual and voice
Information level	Information provided by the TLA service	Information provided by the TLA service, traffic events and POI	Information provided by the TLA service, traffic events and POI

Table 23 CS2 market simulation second service configurations

The resulting graph from these configurations:

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Figure 38 CS2 second market simulation

Finally, in order to illustrate the importance of the information type attribute, a third configuration was created modifying this attribute in the intermediate service to be only “GLOSA”:

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Information type	TTG	GLOSA	GLOSA and TTG
Device	Smartphone	Smartphone and car dashboard	Smartphone and car dashboard
Operating system	Android	iOS and Android	iOS and Android
Notification type	Visual	Voice	Visual and voice
Information level	Information provided by the TLA service	Information provided by the TLA service, traffic events and POI	Information provided by the TLA service, traffic events and POI

Table 24 CS2 market simulation third service configurations

The resulting graph from these configurations:

Figure 39 CS2 third market simulation

As we can see the product 2 goes back to the third position showing that users have a high preference for the TTG information even when the rest of the attributes are configured as more optimal (running another simulation “upgrading” the rest of the attributes to be equal than in the all-in service but keeping the notification type as only “GLOSA” still place the product 2 in third position).

The results extracted from case study one show the following conclusions:

- A Traffic Light Assistance service is still perceived as an “intrusion” into the driver’s control of the vehicle and the information provided by the service is going to highly affect users’ acceptance. Users prefer information they can manage rather than information showing them “what to do”.
- A technical aspect such as the operating system or the way the information is delivered affects importantly the service acceptability; this is more noticeable in younger users.
- Users prefer the information delivered in their smartphones rather than integrated in the car dashboard.

4.4 Case Study 3

4.4.1 Number of respondents

Case study 3 had 37 total respondents. The respondents are segmented as follows:

Figure 40 CS3 company type segmentation

Company type	Respondents	%
Shipper	7	19%
Freight forwarder	6	16%
Carrier truck	2	5%
Inland shipping	1	3%
Inland terminal operator	2	5%

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Sea terminal operator		0%
Warehousing	10	27%
Shipping company		0%
Other	9	24%

Table 25 CS3 company type segmentation

Figure 41 CS3 function within the company segmentation

Function within the company	Respondents	%
Logistic employee	2	5%
Logistic manager	16	43%
Customer service	2	5%
General manager	6	16%
Chain employee / dispatcher		0%
IT Manager		0%
Other	11	30%

Table 26 CS3 function within the company segmentation

Figure 42 CS3 number of containers segmentation

Number of containers	Respondents	%
Less than 50 TEU per year	3	8%
50-100 TEU per year	2	5%
100-500 TEU per year	3	8%
500-1.000 TEU per year	5	14%
1.000-5.000 TEU per year	6	16%
5.000-10.000 TEU per year	8	22%
10.000-50.000 TEU per year	4	11%
More than 50.000 TEU per year	6	16%

Table 27 CS3 number of containers segmentation

Figure 43 CS3 share of container terminal segmentation

Share of containers terminal	Respondents	%
Less than 50%	14	38%
More than 50%	20	54%
None	3	8%

Table 28 CS3 share of container terminal segmentation

4.4.2 Importance

The general attributes importance can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 44 CS3 general attributes importance

The results show that price is the most important attribute for the end-users closely followed by the capacity of tracking the truck in the last-mile (along with tracking the truck as alternative of inland shipping). The notification of deviations is also a quite important attribute composing a final result of end-users valuing the core functionality of the service (track-and-trace of containers) and the price for the service as the most important feature. We could say that end-users perceive the other attributes (shipment coverage, communication options, information container condition and ability to select containers) as bonus or extra functionalities of the service.

The segmented results:

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Figure 45 CS3 attributes importance by company type

When analysing the different types of companies within the logistic chain, we can see that some companies value the importance of the attribute “notification of deviations” and “tracking truck transport” equally or even more important than the price of the service. Although it is hard to draw any conclusion from the single response, it is notable that the tracking of truck transport is rather important for the inland shipping company (with a 39.4% vs. the 19.6% average of the price attribute). Also for the most other companies (except carrier truck companies, probably because they have already their own systems in use) the “tracking truck” attribute is valued almost equally or more importantly than the price attribute. The attribute “notification of deviations” is also perceived as more important than the price by freight forwarders (29.2%), carrier truck (26.9%) and inland terminal operators (23.2%). Most others value this attribute very close to the average value for the price attribute.

Figure 46 CS3 attributes importance by function within the company

Segmentation by function allows analysing the different priorities derived from the role each person is playing within the logistic chain. For customer service, it is very important that most

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

of the shipments are covered by the service as well as the possibility of tracking the truck transport (they value the most the improvement provided by the service in order to satisfy their customers' needs). For logistic managers and employees, the importance relies in managing the containers and doing it in an efficient manner (with notification of deviations, tracking truck and price as the most relevant attributes). In this case is also noticeable how the role of each player affects the value for the attributes, with logistic employees valuing more the communication (since it impacts directly in their daily work) meanwhile logistic managers value more the notification of deviations and the ability it provides in order to plan and re-schedule their operations for a better performance.

Figure 47 CS3 attributes importance by number of containers

We can extract some useful information from this segmentation part of the conjoint results. Apparently, for small companies (with 100 or less TEU per year) the most important feature is the truck tracking attribute (probably because they don't have any other system already in use or because they perceive the current service as better of what they are using at the moment) with importance values of 30.7% and 35.1% versus the 16.1% and 15.1% for the price. It seems that small companies are in high demand of this kind of service and probably it could be a good market place to get in, overall considering they seem to find the price ranges initially defined by the service as reasonable.

It is also very interesting to observe that in this case, the price for the service is by far the most valued attribute for medium companies (1.000-5.000 TEU per year) with a 35.2% which probably is derived from these companies already using other systems in order to provide similar or partially similar service and then, requiring a careful fine-tuning of the price to make the service more attractive for them.

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Figure 48 CS3 attributes importance by share of containers

In this case the different segments are similar to the general values although we can observe that the average importance for tracking truck transport (23.7%) is higher than the average importance for price (18.7%) and the average importance for Notification of deviations (18.4%). Also, we can observe that the attribute price is more important for companies making relatively more use of inland terminals.

4.4.3 Utility summary

Figure 49 CS3 coverage of shipments levels utility

The service covering as much shipments as possible is the most preferred option of the coverage of shipments attribute. The attractiveness of the service seems to increase almost equally moving from 70% to 85% coverage than from 85% to 95% values.

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Figure 50 CS3 communication via service dashboard levels utility

For the communication functionality the chat and documentation option is the preferred option. However, going from no communication to a chat function is a more important step to add value to the service than going from chat function only to chat with documentation available.

Figure 51 CS3 notification of deviations levels utility

The values for the notification of deviations levels show that real-time notification is the preferred option. However, going from no messaging to a daily overview of deviations is a more important step than going from a daily overview to real time push messages on deviations.

Figure 52 CS3 container condition levels utility

In case of the container condition levels, the step going from no information to including container condition based on manual registration is about equally important to add value as the step going from manual registration to manual and sensor information.

Figure 53 CS3 price levels utility

The results on the price, being one of the most important attributes, show that a 10€ price reduction is valued more importantly going from 20€ to 10€ per container than going from 30€ to 20€ per container.

4.4.4 CS3 market simulation and conclusions

Similarly than in previous case studies, the market simulation was performed creating 3 different service configurations, basic, intermediate (including the preferred levels of the most important attributes) and all-in. A “none” option has been included in order to show the market share of users not interested in the service:

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Coverage of shipments	70% of shipments	85% of shipments	95% of shipments
Communication via service dashboard	Not via service	Chat function	Chat function and documents
Notification of deviations	No active messaging	Daily overview of deviations	Push message about deviations
Container condition	No info	Manual registrations	Manual and sensor information
Container selection	Not possible	Possible	Possible
Tracking truck transport	Excluding truck transport	Including truck transport	Including truck transport

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Price	10€ / container	20€ / container	30€ / container

Table 29 CS3 market simulation first service configurations

The resulting share of preference using these configurations:

Figure 54 CS3 initial market simulation

As we can see the intermediate service is showing a good acceptance over the basic service but the share of the users not interested in the service is quite high. In this case we had to be a bit more aggressive changing the levels of the most important attributes to show noticeable changes. As expected, the price is highly affecting the acceptability of the service. In a second configuration, we defined the intermediate service “upgrading” the most important attributes and “downgrading” the rest:

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Coverage of shipments	70% of shipments	95% of shipments	95% of shipments
Communication via service dashboard	Not via service	Not via service	Chat function and documents
Notification of deviations	No active messaging	Push message about deviations	Push message about deviations
Container condition	No info	No info	Manual and sensor information
Container selection	Not possible	Not possible	Possible
Tracking truck transport	Excluding truck transport	Including truck transport	Including truck transport
Price	10€ / container	10€ / container	30€ / container

Table 30 CS3 market simulation second service configurations

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

The resulting graph from these configurations:

Figure 55 CS2 second market simulation

Finally, we changed back some of the “downgraded” levels in order to check the result:

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Coverage of shipments	70% of shipments	95% of shipments	95% of shipments
Communication via service dashboard	Not via service	Chat function	Chat function and documents
Notification of deviations	No active messaging	Push message about deviations	Push message about deviations
Container condition	No info	Manual registration	Manual and sensor information
Container selection	Not possible	Not possible	Possible
Tracking truck transport	Excluding truck transport	Including truck transport	Including truck transport
Price	10€ / container	10€ / container	30€ / container

Table 31 CS3 market simulation third service configurations

The resulting graph from these configurations:

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Figure 56 CS3 third market simulation

As we can see the price is marking a big difference. If we increase the price in this configuration to 20€ per container, the graph goes back to be really similar to the first market simulation, even when the coverage of shipments and the notification of deviations are better in this case. After running some more simulations we found out that accompanying the raise in price to 20€ with the capacity of selecting which containers are going to be tracked swifts the graph back to product 2 being more preferred than the product 3.

In this case we ran an additional simulation to illustrate the importance of the tracking truck transport attribute regarding the price. We tool the previous simulation, increased the price to 20€ per container but configured the service as excluding truck transport:

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Coverage of shipments	70% of shipments	95% of shipments	95% of shipments
Communication via service dashboard	Not via service	Chat function	Chat function and documents
Notification of deviations	No active messaging	Push message about deviations	Push message about deviations
Container condition	No info	Manual registration	Manual and sensor information
Container selection	Not possible	Not possible	Possible
Tracking truck transport	Excluding truck transport	Excluding truck transport	Including truck transport
Price	10€ / container	10€ / container	30€ / container

Table 32 CS3 market simulation forth service configurations

The resulting graph:

Figure 57 CS3 forth market simulation

The acceptability of the product 2 drops significantly even when the price is still 10€ per container and the rest of attributes are also the same. In this case, even “upgrading” the container selection to possible is not going to affect things too much, changing the graph to position product 2 slightly better than in the first market simulation. Configuring product 2 and equally than product 3 but excluding the tracking truck transport and dropping the price to 10€ per container still places the product 2 in second position.

The results extracted from CS3 show the following conclusions:

- Companies within the logistic chain are in great need of tracking services. This need is importantly affected by the price they have to pay for the use of the service, affecting more the medium and big companies as it impacts the volumes they operate with proportionally.
- With more accurate and detailed tracking information, the service acceptability is higher. The capacity of tracking the transport in the last mile is highly appreciated by the users and should be prioritised over the rest of the service features.
- Establishing a service per container seems to work well for small companies but providing another monetisation model or offering volume discounts is going to help the service with medium and big companies. Another option could be to use the container selection capacity in order to serve as a discount feature for the user.
- The different roles within the company affect the perception and acceptability of service among their users. Since the service provides different types of information (transport tracking, container condition, communication and inclusion of relevant documents) a “bundle” offering could benefit the service allowing to configure it depending on the user needs. Although it could be complex, making the price vary depending on the users’ selection of the bundle components could also benefit the service.

4.5 Case Study 4

4.5.1 Number of respondents

Case study 4 had a total of 29 respondents. The respondents are segmented as follows:

Figure 58 CS4 region segmentation

Region	Respondents	%
London	1	3%
West Midlands	3	10%
East Midlands	1	3%
South East	2	7%
North West		0%
Other	22	76%

Table 33 CS4 region segmentation

Figure 59 CS4 transport mode segmentation

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Transport mode	Respondents	%
Passenger	10	34%
Freight	4	14%
Both	15	52%

Table 34 CS4 transport mode segmentation

Figure 60 CS4 distance segmentation

Distance	Respondents	%
Long distance	2	7%
Short distance	4	14%
Both	23	79%

Table 35 CS4 distance segmentation

4.5.2 Importance

The general attributes importance can be seen in the following figure:

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Figure 61 CS4 general attributes importance

The results show that end-users give the most importance to the safety and value for money. They rest of attributes are valued more or less equally with a slight preference for the reputation attribute.

The segmented results:

Figure 62 CS4 attributes importance by region

In this case the London and East Midlands segments give the most importance to lower cost/price in fee for the infrastructure (54.6% and 55% respectively). West Midlands gives the most importance to value for money (39.3%) which is also a high important attribute for East Midlands (41.8%).

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Figure 63 CS4 attributes importance by transport mode

In this case the results show a high predominance of the importance in the safety attribute given by the freight transport, followed by reputation. Passenger transport, conceding the most importance to safety, also gives high importance to value for money and journey reliability.

Figure 64 CS4 attributes importance by distance

Long distance segment gives high importance to value for money and lower cost/price fee for the infrastructure. Companies providing both short and long distance trips give more importance to safety and value for money.

4.5.3 Utility summary

Figure 65 CS4 value for money levels utility

The service is perceived as profitable if it improves the revenues at least by 3% and this added value grows linearly with the increase in revenues, moving similarly from an increase from 1% to 2% than from 2% to 3%.

Figure 66 CS4 journey reliability levels utility

The end-users perceive as an improvement provided by the service the reduction in delayed trips of at least 3%. In this case the value of moving from 1% to 3% fewer delays is perceived as more important than moving from 3% to 5% which could indicate that end-users perceive a maximum threshold derived from the service.

Figure 67 CS4 safety levels utility

The end-users would prefer having a reduction in the number of accidents with the identification of the cause as a main option. Interestingly, the step moving towards receiving information from the cause of an accident from a just reducing the number of accidents (with no information about the causes) is perceived almost as important as the step moving towards the reduction of accidents (with no information of the causes) from a no overall reduction of accidents. This indicates the high value given by the end-users to the information, adding a new dimension to the safety attribute.

Figure 68 CS4 lower cost/price in fee for infrastructure levels utility

The end users perceive an advantage provided by the service a cost reduction in the infrastructure fee by at least a 5% but moving from a cost reduction of 2% to 5% is perceived as more valuable than moving from 5% to 7%, reinforcing again the idea of the maximum threshold coming from the service.

Figure 69 CS4 reputation levels utility

In case of reputation, any improvement is perceived as positive by the end-users. Moving from no reputation to a 3% increase is perceived as more valuable than moving from 3% to 5% and even when in this case this could be justified by the numbers, it again seems to demonstrate a perception of maximum threshold on the service.

4.5.4 CS4 market simulation and conclusions

In the same way than in the rest of case studies, a market simulation is presented using 3 different service configurations, basic, intermediate (including the preferred levels of the most important attributes) and all-in. A “none” option has been included in order to show the market share of users not interested in the service:

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Value for money	1% increase in revenue	2% increase of revenue	3% increase in revenue
Journey reliability	1% less delays in services	3% less delays in services	5% less delay in services
Safety	No overall reduction of accidents	Reduction of accidents but with no identification of the causes	Reduction of accidents with identification of the causes
Lower cost/price in fee for the infrastructure	Cost reduction by 2%	Cost reduction by 5%	Cost reduction by 7%
Reputation	No increase	3% increase in travellers/freight	5% increase in travellers/freight

Table 36 CS4 market simulation first service configurations

The resulting share of preference using these configurations:

Figure 70 CS4 initial market simulation

In this case, the all-in service is also getting a much higher preference over the other 2 products. Is also noticeable high acceptance of the service itself (probably also derived from the lack of cost versus the obvious benefits obtained from the service). After running some more simulations we found out that in order to reduce this gap between the intermediate and the all-in services, is not enough only increasing the directly-oriented financial attributes:

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Value for money	1% increase in revenue	3% increase of revenue	3% increase in revenue
Journey reliability	1% less delays in services	3% less delays in services	5% less delay in services
Safety	No overall reduction of accidents	Reduction of accidents but with no identification of the causes	Reduction of accidents with identification of the causes
Lower cost/price in fee for the infrastructure	Cost reduction by 2%	Cost reduction by 7%	Cost reduction by 7%
Reputation	No increase	5% increase in travellers/freight	5% increase in travellers/freight

Table 37 CS4 market simulation second service configurations

The resulting graph from these configurations:

Figure 71 CS4 second market simulation

But interestingly using the first intermediate configuration and only increasing the safety attribute to “Reduction of accidents with identification of the causes” shows very similar results (with a 23.5% preference for the product 2 and a 72.3% for the product 3). This shows that the security aspects of the service are very highly valued and also could be considered as a reinforcement of the maximum threshold perception of the users in the financial benefits.

Finally, in order to illustrate this importance on the safety attribute, a third configuration was created equalling the intermediate configuration to the all-in configuration in all levels except the safety:

	Product 1	Product 2	Product 3
Value for money	1% increase in revenue	3% increase of revenue	3% increase in revenue
Journey reliability	1% less delays in services	5% less delays in services	5% less delay in services
Safety	No overall reduction of accidents	Reduction of accidents but with no identification of the causes	Reduction of accidents with identification of the causes
Lower cost/price in fee for the infrastructure	Cost reduction by 2%	Cost reduction by 7%	Cost reduction by 7%
Reputation	No increase	5% increase in travellers/freight	5% increase in travellers/freight

Table 38 CS4 market simulation third service configurations

The resulting graph from these configurations:

Figure 72 CS4 third market simulation

As we can see the product 2, counting with the rest of advantages as the product 3 except the identification of the accident causes, is much less preferred, illustrating the importance of the safety attribute and how this affects the service acceptability.

The results extracted from case study one show the following conclusions:

- A predictive maintenance service counts with great base acceptance given the great benefits it can provide not only in safety but also considering the financial benefits obtained.

- A clear conclusion of the results is that information is one of the strong points of the service, especially security information. Identifying the causes of an accident is valuable information which highly increases the service acceptability.
- Despite being a subjective opinion, it seems to be a maximum threshold perceived on the service by the users, mainly in the financial benefits obtained. It is worth to deeply investigate about the presence of this threshold perception in order to increase the users' acceptability when monetizing the service. Providing reliable estimations about the benefits (given for example the company size or other affecting factors) could be a good marketing strategy.
- In a similar way, it is also worth considering to offer the service at a reduced price initially and adjust the price depending on the results obtained during the "trial-period" since the costs derived of deploying the service with reduced functionality are not very high compared with the potential benefits (both for the end-users and the service owner) obtained.

4.6 Gender analysis of the NEWBITS Case Studies

This section focuses on identifying any possible gaps in gender relations and roles in the context of the validated case studies, providing the overall results of the evaluation from WP2 and WP3. As already elaborated in D1.1, the gender analysis plan in NEWBITS follows a checklist approach, with the questions specifically oriented to WP2 being:

- a. How catalytic are the case studies in advancing women's well-being, empowerment and gender equality?
- b. Having framed the application areas of the case studies, do the contexts suggest different patterns of use by different groups of potential consumers (men-women)?

And the questions specifically oriented to WP3:

- a. Potential consumers of technology and services have different characteristics. What role, if any, do gender play with regard to the case studies?
- b. Having framed the application areas of the case studies, do the contexts suggest different patterns of use by different groups of potential consumers (men-women)?
- c. Might different groups of potential consumers (men-women) have different expectations regarding interface, features and functions?
- d. Is there a risk of excluding certain groups (men or woman) through the case study design?
- e. What are the relevant gender variables to consider market conditioners for the case studies, and what information is relevant or we don't know or understand concerning gender?

4.6.1 CS1 gender dimension

In CS1, the end-users are men or woman indistinctly with similar patterns of use. Gender has been one of the segmentations selected by the use case in the performance of the conjoint

analysis and showed that the preferences from all segments are quite similar not showing different expectations and no risk of exclusion.

4.6.2 CS2 gender dimension

Gender was also considered as a factor of segmentation in CS2. In this case, we can observe very small differences from both genders although considering the potential market and even counting that both males and females preferences are almost equal for all the attributes of the service, men tend to give slightly more importance to the type of information provided by the service meanwhile women are a bit more concerned than men about the operating system of the device providing the service.

4.6.3 CS3 gender dimension

In CS3, the product/service does not represent any difference in terms of usage or acceptability by men and women, neither seems to be any market conditioner depending on the gender.

4.6.4 CS4 gender dimension

Similar to CS3, CS4 product/service is designed to be used equally by men and woman and there is no identified relevant pattern of usage or market conditioner of the service affected by the gender.

5 Conclusions and lessons learned

Conjoint analysis has proven to be a very useful method in extracting valuable information about customers' preferences, allowing the shaping of a product/service into something successful and being of great help when creating new business models.

When performing a conjoint analysis, the definition of the appropriate attributes and levels, along with selection of the correct segmentation, impacts directly in the usefulness of the results extracted from the study. It is well worth to spend more time in the first steps of the conjoint (especially in the problem definition step) to guarantee that the results are going to be representative for the final purpose of the study.

Respondents' exhaustion should not be underestimated. Even counting with a good initial sample size, a bad configuration in the data gathering process can lead to a high percentage of uncomplete surveys reducing the final sample size to a portion of what was estimated initially.

Conjoint analysis is an overall complex technique involving several statistical and mathematical methods. It is advisable to evaluate the ability of the researchers and the sample size when deciding how the study is going to be implemented. Commercial tools are of invaluable help if the study is either very complex (involving many attributes, levels, etc.) or if the sample size is big enough to become overwhelming in case of using semi-automatic tools.

In NEWBITS the results of the conjoint analysis over the project case studies are perfectly complementing the results of the market analysis performed in D3.1 and establish a good basis for the creation of new business models and the cost-benefit analysis. The main conclusions per case study could be summarised as follows:

- Case study one: In a carpooling service implemented in a specific area, the capacity of promising parking space (even when it is not guaranteed during all periods) is highly ranked by their end-users. A users' identification functionality contributes in building trust in the service and improves the willingness of using it. Any communication functionality is also very appreciated by the end-users.
- Case study two: A Traffic Light Assistance service could still be perceived as an "intrusion" into the driver's control of the vehicle. It is important to carefully configure how the information is provided in order to increase the end-users acceptability of the service. Younger people, more in contact with technology, give high importance to the technical characteristics of the service (such as how the information is delivered and which devices provide this information). The results of the study are in line with other studies where drivers ask for "information I can directly use".
- Case study three: a service providing tracking and optimising of freight container transport should be fine-tuned based on the company size and role the company plays in the logistic chain. The results of the study indicate that small companies are in great need of tracking services, meanwhile medium companies are less receptive to acquire such a service unless its price is adjusted to something making profitable their daily operations. The position of the company within the logistic chain and the role of the end-user in the company are a clear differentiator in which features of the service are considered as high-valuable. Overall, the service could potentially benefit

of an offering as a bundle with high level of configuration depending on the end-users' needs.

- Case study four: A predictive maintenance service designed for rail transport is perceived as a benefit mainly because the overall safety increase and the financial improvement in terms of value for money and journey reliability. Since the benefits of the service are obvious but hardly quantifiable, focusing in a unique selling point such as providing reliable estimations could establish a good selling strategy.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 Case studies CBC surveys samples

Case study 1

Si estas fueran las únicas opciones, ¿Cuál escogería?

3 / 12

Case study 2

Quale delle seguenti opzioni è di tuo interesse?

3 / 12

Tipologia di informazione	TTG	GLOSA	GLOSA e TTG	
Dispositivo	Sul cruscotto del veicolo	Smartphone	Smartphone e sul cruscotto del veicolo	
Sistema operativo	Android	iOS	iOS e Android	Nessuna delle opzioni precedenti.
Tipo di notifica	Vocale	Visiva	Visiva	
Livello di informazione	Informazioni fornite dal servizio TLA	Informazioni fornite dal servizio TLA ed eventi di traffico	Informazioni fornite dal servizio TLA ed eventi di traffico	
	<input type="button" value="Seleziona"/>	<input type="button" value="Seleziona"/>	<input type="button" value="Seleziona"/>	<input type="button" value="Seleziona"/>

← →

0% 100%

Case study 3

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Welk van onderstaande opties beschouwd u als meest interessant?

3 / 15

Dekkingsgraad shipments	95% van shipments	70% van shipments	85% van shipments	
Communicatie via service dashboard	Chatfunctie	Geen via service	Chatfunctie en documenten	
Berichtgeving afwijkingen	Dagelijks overzicht afwijkingen	Geen actieve berichtgeving	Push-bericht over afwijking	
Containerconditie	o.b.v. handmatige en sensorinformatie	o.b.v. handmatige registraties	Geen info	NONE: Geen van de opties
Containerselectie	Niet mogelijk	Wel mogelijk	Niet mogelijk	
Tracking van trucktransport	Exclusief trucktransport	Inclusief trucktransport	Exclusief trucktransport	
Prijs	€20 / container	€30 / container	€10 / container	
	Select	Select	Select	Select

← →

0% 100%

Case study 4

If these were your only options, which would you choose?

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Value for money	2% increase in revenue	3% increase in revenue	1% increase in revenue	
Journey reliability	5% less delays in services	1% less delays in services	3% less delays in services	
Safety	No overall reduction of accidents	Reduction of accidents but no identification of the causes	Reduction of accidents with identification of the causes	NONE: I wouldn't choose any of these.
Lower cost/price in fee for infrastructure	Cost reduction by 5%	Cost reduction by 2%	Cost reduction by 7%	
Reputation	5% increase in travellers/freight	3% increase in travellers/freight	5% increase in travellers/freight	
	Select	Select	Select	Select

Appendix 2 full conjoint results

Case study 1

Attributes importance (general)

category	value
Parking access	28,7
Messaging	17,1
Users rating	10,8
Users identification	17,7
Travellers matching	13,6
Information on environmental savings	12,1

Attributes importance (age)

category	value0	value1	value2	value3	value4
Parking access	28	27,3	30,2	32,8	34
Messaging	17,8	17	15,9	14,1	11,9
Users rating	11,1	12,4	9,7	9,3	10
Users identification	16,8	19,5	19,2	17,2	27
Travellers matching	14,1	12,5	13,2	13	4,6
Information on environmental savings	12,2	11,3	11,8	13,6	12,6

Attributes importance (gender)

category	value0	value1	value2
Parking access	29,1	28,4	29,4
Messaging	17,8	16,6	21,2
Users rating	10,2	11,2	11,9
Users identification	17,8	17,6	16,8
Travellers matching	12,6	14,2	7,7
Information on environmental savings	12,5	11,9	13,1

Attributes importance (relation UAB)

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

category	value0	value1	value2	value3	value4
Parking access	28,1	30,4	29,3	29,9	28,9
Messaging	17,7	15,4	16,1	28,2	17,5
Users rating	11,3	9,3	10,5	0,3	17,4
Users identification	16,9	19,4	19,4	40	14,7
Travellers matching	14,2	12	12,8	0,8	10,9
Information on en...	11,9	13,4	11,8	0,8	10,5

Attributes importance (trip frequency)

category	value0	value1	value2	value3
Parking access	28,8	28,9	20,9	27,3
Messaging	17,1	16,4	19,7	18,4
Users rating	10,7	12	10,7	10,4
Users identification	17,8	16,6	24,3	15,9
Travellers matching	13,6	13,3	12,7	14,4
Information on environmental savings	12	12,8	11,6	13,7

Attributes importance (trip distance)

category	value0	value1	value2
Parking access	29,2	28,2	28,2
Messaging	16,8	17,1	18,3
Users rating	10,7	10,9	11,7
Users identification	17,6	18,1	16,8
Travellers matching	13,5	13,7	13,4
Information on environmental savings	12,3	12	11,6

Levels utility (parking access)

category	value
No	-77,9
Not in rush	-16,3

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

hours	
Always	94,1

Levels utility (Messaging)

category	value
No	-54,9
Only incidents	7,4
Chat	47,5

Levels utility (users' rating)

category	value
No	-32,6
Yes	32,6

Levels utility (users' identification)

category	value
No	-53,1
Access only with NIU UAB	53,1

Levels utility (travel matching)

category	value
No	-40,7
Yes, according preferences and likings	40,7

Levels utility (environmental savings information)

category	value
None	-39,4
Simple	6,2
Complete	33,2

Case study 2

Attributes importance (general)

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

category	value
Information type	43,7
Device	13,7
Operating system	19,4
Notification type	16,3
Information level	6,9

Attributes importance (gender)

category	value0	value1
Information type	47	40,4
Device	13,6	13,8
Operating system	17,6	21,3
Notification type	15,6	17
Information level	6,2	7,6

Attributes importance (age)

category	value0	value1	value2	value3	value4
Information type	22,3	47	49,5	48,3	53,1
Device	17,3	11,8	12,8	13,4	13,2
Operating system	30,5	18,6	16,4	16,3	14,5
Notification type	20,3	15,4	14,3	16,7	14,7
Information level	9,6	7,3	7	5,4	4,5

Attributes importance (level of income)

category	value0	value1	value2	value3	value4	value5	value6
Information type	23,9	41,8	41,1	44,5	47,5	52,1	45,3
Device	15,7	16,2	13,6	13,2	13,1	14	12,5
Operating system	33	14,4	23,4	16,5	19	14,6	19,1
Notification type	19,1	18,1	14,1	17,7	15,2	14	16,9
Information level	8,2	9,5	7,8	8,1	5,2	5,3	6,2

Attributes importance (trip purpose)

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

category	value0	value1	value2	value3	value4
Information type	44,1	39,7	50,3	43,7	46,9
Device	13,9	13,6	13,5	14	13,4
Operating system	18,6	23,4	15,7	17,4	15
Notification type	16	16,1	14,7	18	22,1
Information level	7,5	7,2	5,8	6,9	2,7

Attributes importance (trip distance)

category	value0	value1	value2	value3	value4	value5
Information type	36,1	39,5	49,5	53,4	42,3	33,3
Device	18,8	13,1	13,1	12,2	14	15,1
Operating system	24,9	21,6	15	14,9	19,3	26,2
Notification type	13,9	18,8	16,6	12,9	16,1	18,4
Information level	6,3	7,1	5,8	6,7	8,4	7

Levels utility (information type)

category	value
GLOSA	-38,8
TTG	-6,3
GLOSA and TTG	45,1

Levels utility (device)

category	value
Smartphone	-2,2
Car dashboard	-6,1
Smartphone and car dashboard	8,3

Levels utility (operating system)

category	value
iOS	-14,1
Android	2,3
iOS and Android	11,9

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Levels utility (notification type)

category	value
Visual	-4,6
Voice	-1,9
Visual and voice	6,5

Levels utility (information level)

category	value
TLA	-17,2
TLA and traffic	0
TLA traffic and POI	17,2

Case study 3

Attributes importance (general)

category	value
Coverage of shipments	13,3
Communication via service dashboard	8,4
Notification of deviations	18,6
Container condition	7,3
Container selection	10,5
Tracking truck transport	20,3
Price	21,6

Attributes importance (company type)

category	value0	value1	value2	value3	value4	value5	value6
Coverage of shipments	13,8	7,3	8,9	13,1	9,6	16,4	15,7
Communication via service dashboard	8,7	11,2	13,5	11,4	4,8	6,2	8,1
Notification of deviations	14,8	29,2	26,9	16	23,2	18,7	15,2
Container condition	7,1	9	12,7	0,4	5,2	5,8	7,8
Container selection	13,7	6,5	8,9	19,3	17,6	9,3	8,9

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Tracking truck transport	23,6	20,5	11,5	39,4	22,2	18,7	21,1
Price	18,4	16,3	17,6	0,3	17,5	25	23,3

Attributes importance (function within the company)

category	value0	value1	value2	value3	value4
Coverage of shipments	13,2	15,5	22,6	10,6	10,2
Communication via service dashboard	14,9	7,2	3,6	9,3	9,3
Notification of deviations	11,2	19,8	16	23,2	19
Container condition	5,9	5,5	4,2	11,5	8,3
Container selection	9,7	10,5	10,8	6,8	11,8
Tracking truck transport	21,9	15,9	25,6	23,3	25,6
Price	23,2	25,6	17,1	15,2	15,8

Attributes importance (number of containers)

category	value0	value1	value2	value3	value4	value5	value6	value7
Coverage of shipments	4,3	12,9	13,4	17,8	12,7	12,3	16,2	14,7
Communication via service dashboard	10,3	11,2	11,1	4,4	5,9	13	6,7	5,9
Notification of d...	15,3	14,4	25,1	14,1	17,4	20,6	14,4	28,6
Container condition	11,4	5,4	1,6	6,9	6,2	8,4	10,5	6,1
Container selection	11,9	5,8	13,8	13,6	8	10	7,3	10,9
Tracking truck transport	30,7	35,1	15,6	23,4	14,4	15,4	23,2	23,7
Price	16,1	15,1	19,4	19,7	35,2	20,2	21,8	10,1

Attributes importance (share of containers)

category	value0	value1	value2
Coverage of shipments	13,3	14,8	4,3
Communication via service dashboard	7,5	8,7	10,3
Notification of deviations	21,1	18,9	15,3
Container condition	6,8	6,9	11,4
Container selection	13,4	7,9	11,9

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Tracking truck transport	22,1	18,5	30,7
Price	15,8	24,4	16,1

Levels utility (coverage of shipments)

category	value
70% of shipments	-47,1
85% of shipments	0,9
95% of shipments	46,1

Levels utility (communication via dashboard)

category	value
Not via service	-32,4
Chat function	6,1
Chat function and documents	26,3

Levels utility (notification of deviations)

category	value
No active messaging	-77,2
Daily overview of...	24,1
Push message about deviations	53,2

Levels utility (container conditions)

category	value
No info	-24,7
Manual registrations	-1,7
Manual and sensor information	26,4

Levels utility (container selection)

category	value
Not possible	-36,6

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Possible	36,6
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Levels utility (tracking truck)

category	value
Excluding truck transport	-71
Including truck transport	71

Levels utility (price)

category	value
€30 / container	-70,6
€20 / container	-10,2
€10 / container	80,8

Case study 4

Attributes importance (general)

category	value
Value for money	22,8
Journey reliability	14,3
Safety	32,6
Lower cost/price in fee for the infrastructure	13,2
Reputation	17,1

Attributes importance (region)

category	value0	value1	value2	value3	value4
Value for money	1,2	39,3	41,8	25,1	20,5
Journey reliability	35,9	17,2	0,9	7	14,2
Safety	1,4	20,8	1,3	57,9	34,7
Lower cost/price in fee for the infrastructure	54,6	12,9	55	9,2	9,8
Reputation	6,9	9,8	0,9	0,8	20,8

Attributes importance (transport mode)

category	value0	value1	value2
Value for money	22,3	10,9	26,4
Journey reliability	19,5	4	13,6
Safety	33,5	47,7	27,9
Lower cost/price in fee for the infrastructure	15,8	14,6	11
Reputation	8,8	22,9	21,1

Attributes importance (distance)

category	value0	value1	value2
Value for money	42,7	22,7	21,1
Journey reliability	0,8	19,5	14,6
Safety	13	34,5	33,9
Lower cost/price in fee for the infrastructure	41	11,6	11
Reputation	2,5	11,7	19,4

Levels utility (value for money)

category	value
3% increase in revenue	61,3
2% increase in revenue	-8,4
1% increase in revenue	-52,9

Levels utility (journey reliability)

category	value
5% less delays in services	33,1
3% less delays in services	5,4
1% less delays in services	-38,4

Levels utility (safety)

category	value
Reduction of accidents with identification of the causes	80,3

D3.3 Conjoint analysis on case studies

Reduction of accidents but with no identification of the causes	2,2
No overall reduction of accidents	-82,6

Levels utility (lower cost/price in fee for infrastructure)

category	value
Cost reduction by 7%	32,1
Cost reduction by 5%	1,5
Cost reduction by 2%	-33,6

Levels utility (reputation)

category	value
5% increase in travellers/freight	40,7
3% increase in travellers/freight	4,2
No increase	-44,9

Appendix 3 Sawtooth software discover component

Sawtooth software, the leading provider of conjoint analysis software worldwide, has developed a SaaS (Software as a Service) questionnaire and CBC tool that is streamlined, attractive and especially useful for both classroom use and standard CBC studies in industry.

The discover-CBC component resides on a web server provided by a reliable third party so the user does not need to install any software and simply logs into the service using a browser connected to the internet. All questionnaire, data collection and analysis occur in the web server. Results may be downloaded to the user's local device and opened in a program such as Excel.

The software lets the questionnaire author compose standard questions in addition to the CBC tasks, such as text screens (requiring no response), select-questions (radio and check box), numeric, grid-type, constant sum and open-end questions. The CBC questions are limited to:

- 8 attributes.
- 15 levels per attribute.
- No more than 8 concepts (profiles) per choice task.
- No more than 30 tasks per respondents.

Upfront, the questionnaire author must specify which attributes have known (*a priori*) utility order. For attributes without known utility order (such as brand or colour), the software adds rating questions prior the CBC tasks. The *a priori* and stated orders of levels within attributes:

- Serve as utility constraints (monotonicity constraint) to permit robust individual utility estimation (Logit with data augmentation via empirical Bayes).
- Provide individual-level preference information so the software can try to avoid² dominated concepts within the on-the-fly experiment design.

The overall importance of attributes is estimated entirely based on the choices within the CBC tasks.

Discover-CBC includes a recommendation wizard that suggests an appropriate number of tasks and concepts per task to ask, given the specific attribute and level array specified by the questionnaire author. The recommendations are based on Logit theory (specifically, the computation of standard errors) and knowledge drawn from a large variety of experimental designs for CBC. The author may override the suggestions.

The design has an adaptive element, using a random starting point followed by many iterations of level-relabeling and swapping across all attribute levels, concepts and tasks to satisfy multiple simultaneous goals: one-way level balance within attributes, two-way level balance between attributes, target degree of level overlap (specified by the author), avoiding dominated concepts, and avoiding prohibited pairs of levels between attributes (specified by

² The experimental designer simultaneously targets multiple goals, one of which is to avoid dominated concepts. If there are goals that cannot be resolved, some dominated concepts may result. The presence of dominated concepts does not invalidate the results. Standard CBC designs typically include many dominated concepts for individuals.

the author). These designs are near-orthogonal and have high relative D-efficiency, because designs that are one and two-way level balanced also are near-orthogonal and statistically efficient.

The software has the ability for the author to specify how much “level overlap” to use per attribute. By default, all attributes have a modest degree of level overlap (level repeating within a task). Modest level overlap has been found to be beneficial because the following reasons:

- Allowing levels to repeat on occasions within the choice task more deeply probes respondents’ preferences when respondents employ non-compensatory (cut-off) rules – which researchers have found to be a typical respondent behaviour.
- Allowing levels to repeat improves the statistical efficiency on interaction effects³.

In terms of utility estimation Discover-CBC avoid the IIA troubles not using pooled aggregate logit analysis. The software uses maximum likelihood estimation via individual-level logit, subject to monotonicity constraints, with Bayesian smoothing toward population parameters via empirical Bayes.

The main reason for not using hierarchical Bayesian (HB) estimation for utilities on this component is:

- HB places a much larger computational requirement on the servers than the Sawtooth method of empirical Bayes. If hundreds of students submitted via HB jobs simultaneously at midnight on the night before a project was due, the entire system could potentially grind to a crawl.
- Purely individual-level estimation via logit (when leveraging within-attribute ranking information of levels via monotonicity constraints and employing empirical Bayes) can be nearly as accurate as HB models.

³ Discover-CBC software will not automatically estimate interaction effects. However, advanced users may export their data to a CBC/HB ready data file or more advanced analysis.